

Alternative ways of European participatory organic
fruit breeding projects

Valorisation of Greek apple and pear genetic resources and advancing organic fruit breeding

AEGILOPS

Greek Network for Biodiversity
and Ecology in Agriculture

**Funded by
the European Union**

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI**

Funded by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme of the
European Union under grant agreement No 101061028

AEGILOPS and the BIOFru Organic Farm

AEGILOPS is a non-governmental organisation in Greece, founded in 2004, with a mission to conserve and sustainably manage biodiversity, as well as to promote organic agriculture. The main scope of the organisation is to support resilient seed and food systems. AEGILOPS have set up Focal Points in many regions of the country organising local community seed banks and conducting participatory conservation breeding. Regional activities involve training and knowledge dissemination on organic breeding and conservation, characterization and evaluation of local varieties of vegetables, legumes, grains and fruits.

The Greek case study is BioFru organic farm, which is located in Kastoria, in the northwest part of the country. The farm produces apples and pears, as well as quinces, persimmons and chestnuts in an area of 5 ha and at an altitude of 700m. The farm is a family business and currently run by Sevi Liouza (2nd generation farmer). The cultivation is purely organic, and the management includes, also, several regenerative agriculture and agroforestry techniques and practices.

BIOFru organic farm is among AEGILOPS's founders and a Focal Point. Part of the farm is dedicated to AEGILOPS's heritage fruit nursery preserving, currently, 130 apple and 65 pear old cultivars collected mainly from the region of Western Macedonia (Northern Greece), as well as the region of Epirus (Western Greece).

BIO **Fru**

BIOFru Organic Farm

The scope of BIOFru Organic Farm is to advance breeding activities and selection (transition from pre-breeding to breeding protocol validation). Main activities involve final selection of candidate apple and pear cultivars (screening phases of material) and development of a participative breeding program.

The **heritage fruit nursery project began in 2014**, as an effort to slow down the rapid loss of apple and pear genetic wealth through the preservation of old cultivars. In the beginning, the collection was quite small, but, as the years passed and the need for organic cultivars increased, the project acquired a more systematic research approach. Further expeditions were planned to collect old cultivars and to establish an enormous collection from which new organic varieties may be produced, through selection. Basic characterisation and documentation (building up a database) is an ongoing activity, combined with pre-breeding selection activities of candidate organic varieties.

During the **LIVESEED project (2017-2021)**, Aegilops was in charge of an apple task, aiming to organise a **European Network of Organic Fruit Breeders**, and in this context, the BIOFru organic farm was connected for the first time with European organic fruit breeding initiatives and relevant organic fruit stakeholders.

The case study is characterized by various elements of technical and social innovations. At the technological level, the organic agriculture practices applied are enriched by agroforestry and modern regenerative agriculture practices and techniques, while in the field of selection and valorization of PGR organic fruit, pre-breeding methodology and evaluation are followed.

A participatory evaluation approach, multi stakeholder cooperation and open farm days enhance **social innovation and interaction**. Last but not least, there is an annual local farmers' fair organised in Kastoria by Oikotropio (a local Eco farmers' association). BIOFru organic farm plays a crucial role there, as it is a board member of Oikotropio and participates actively in the fair's organising committee.

InnOBreed collaboration

Since 2022, BIOFru Organic Farm is part of the InnOBreed project as a case study, joining a network of European colleagues working in the same field.

The main activities within the InnOBreed project, involve evaluation, preselection of candidate apple and pear cultivars (screening phases of material) and development of a participatory breeding program. Selection will be based on robustness, disease and insect resistance, fruit quality and shelf life. The whole interaction will boost sustainable valorisation of PGR, organic fruit sector and participatory organic fruit breeding in Greece and, through AEGILOPS, in the whole Balkans. Furthermore, the heritage nursery is expected to scale up its activities to cover market, consumer and organic farmers' needs, something that is expected to happen within InnOBreed.

Technological and social innovations will contribute to knowledge transfer, multi-actor interaction and cooperation, farmers' participation and final users' involvement at local and regional level.

Participatory organic fruit breeding methodology and models shared within InnOBreed will help AEGILOPS create analogous initiatives in other crops and regions where community seed banks and organic farmers interact at local level trying to build up resilient food systems and mitigate climate change impacts.

The activities of AEGILOPS's case study and BIOFru organic farm contribute to InnOBreed objective of designing adapted ideotypes for current and future agroecological areas and assess the prioritisation of the relevant traits. The Greek case study reflects needs and special characteristics/traits of adapted organic fruit cultivars to geographical zone of Balkan peninsula and relevant climatic zones, contributing to a broader range of targets for organic fruit breeding within the context of climate change and resilience of agricultural systems. In addition, by dealing with PGR of the Balkans and southeast Europe, InnOBreed broadens its database and the diversity of genetic resources used or future available for organic fruit breeding.

More information is available through the following links:

- BIOFru organic farm website www.biofru.gr
- AEGILOPS's local food website www.aegilopslocalfood.gr/listing/biofru/
- Open farm network website openfarm.gr/farms/biofru-kastoria/

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